

Original version for public

ARTICLE

Intrinsic Structure of Pentapeptide Leu-enkephalin: Geometry Optimization and Validation by Comparison of VSCF Calculations with Cold Ion Spectroscopy

Cite this: DOI:
10.1039/c8cp03989e

Tapta Kanchan Roy,^{*a†} Vladimir Kopysov,^{b†} Aleksandr Y. Pereverzev,^b Jiří Šebek,^c R. Benny Gerber,^d and Oleg V. Boyarkin^{*b}

www.rsc.org/

^a Department of Chemistry and Chemical Sciences, Central University of Jammu, Rahya-Suchani (Bagla), Jammu 181143, India

^b Laboratoire de Chimie Physique Moléculaire, École Polytechnique, Fédérale de Lausanne, 1015 Lausanne, Switzerland. E-mail: oleg.boiarkin@epfl.ch

^c Department of Physical Chemistry, University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague, Czech Republic

^d Institute of Chemistry, The Hebrew University Jerusalem 91904 (Israel) and Department of Chemistry, University of California Irvine, CA 92697, USA. E-mail: benny@fh.huji.ac.il

† Electronic supplementary information (ESI) available. See DOI: 10.1039/c8cp03989e ‡ Authors with equal contribution.

Intrinsic structure of an opioid peptide [Ala², Leu⁵]-leucine enkephalin (ALE) has been investigated using first-principles based vibrational self-consistent field (VSCF) theory and cold ion spectroscopy. The IR-UV double resonance spectroscopy revealed the presence of only one highly abundant conformer of the singly protonated ALE, isolated and cryogenically cooled in the gas phase. High-level quantum mechanical calculations of electronic structures in conjunction with a systematic conformational search allowed for finding a few low-energy candidate structures. In order to identify the observed structure, we computed vibrational spectra of the candidate structures we employed the theory at the semi-empirical harmonic level and at the first-principles based anharmonic VSCF levels. The best match between the calculated “anharmonic” and the measured spectra appeared, indeed, for the most stable candidate. An average of two spectra calculated with different quantum chemical methods is proposed for best match with experiment. The match thus validates the calculated intrinsic structure of ALE and demonstrates the predictive power of the first-principles theory for solving structures of such large molecules.

Introduction

Determination of the three-dimensional (3D) structures and intramolecular interactions in biomolecules with high conformational

heterogeneity remains one of the most challenging and crucial objectives in life science. High-resolution laser spectroscopy of cryogenically cooled gas-phase demonstrates an increasing capability for conformer-specific determinations of intrinsic structures for small to midsize biomolecules.^{1–9} Similar to other

proven techniques, such as NMR, cryogenic electron spectroscopy, and X-ray diffraction, cold ion spectroscopy provides certain number of structural constraints (e.g., IR and/or UV spectra, fragmentation mass spectra), which have to be reproduced by theory for validating a calculated structure. Vibrationally resolved IR spectra are particularly valuable for such validations, as they reflect covalent and non-covalent interactions in the electronic ground state of molecules. IR spectra for midsize peptides are typically calculated in a semi-empirical harmonic oscillator (HO) approximation, which implies a use of empirical scaling factors to account for the intramode/intermode anharmonicity of molecular vibrations in order to match calculations to an experiment. An apparent attractiveness of the HO approximation is its relatively low computational cost compared to first-principles anharmonic calculations. A severe drawback of HO approximations is a reduced number of observed vibrational transitions that can be matched to experimental ones using a single scaling factor. Frequencies of the vibrations that are anharmonically strongly coupled (e.g., due to hydrogen bonds) are known to be particularly difficult to reproduce in HO approximation. On the other hand, the computational cost of the first-principles based quantum chemistry methods, which explicitly account for vibrational anharmonicity, increases rapidly upon increasing the number of molecular vibrations. Affordable, yet accurate algorithms are therefore on high demand to deal with large molecular systems, such as, for instance, oligopeptides. Vibrational self-consistent field (VSCF) approximation^{10, 11} is one such inexpensive, yet practical method that can handle medium to large molecular systems.¹²⁻²¹ It was successfully employed for calculations of small and midsize biomolecules, such as amino acids, mono- and di-saccharides, nucleobases, dipeptides,^{15, 22-25} and even for a decapeptide gramicidin S.^{26, 27} It is yet challenging to apply such algorithm even to pentapeptides because of large number of vibrational modes; suitable potentials do not allow performing the calculation in a reasonable time scale. Other alternatives, such as MD simulations,^{28, 29} perturbation theory,^{30, 31} and rigorous numerical techniques³² are also available and some of them are applied to medium sized biomolecules. For example, the Born-Oppenheimer MD (BOMD) simulations are applied for a few biomolecules by treating nuclei classically and the electrons quantum mechanically by using suitable DFT functional.^{28, 29} Herein we employ VSCF approximation with second-order perturbation corrected algorithm (VSCF-PT2)³³ and the quantum mechanically computed PES for calculating anharmonic IR spectra for a few pre-selected low-energy calculated conformers of protonated peptide [Ala², Leu⁵]-leucine enkephalin (YAGFL-H⁺) with all natural *L*-enantiomers of the residues (denoted ALE below). IR spectra for these structures calculated in scaled-HO and VSCF approximations allow us to assess the accuracy and performance of the two approaches in reproducing the experiment. The candidate structures have been found using a multistep conformational search which allows to reduce computational time while minimizing the chance of missing some of the relevant structures. To validate the results of the computation, the anharmonic spectra have been

compared with the conformer-specific spectrum of ALE measured using cold ion spectroscopy.

Fig.1. Schematic view of [L-Ala2, L-Leu5]-Enkephalin, $m/z = 556.3$ Da

Theoretical methods

Conformational Analysis

ALE (Fig. 1) is a highly flexible molecule which, potentially, may adopt a large number of low energy conformers. There is a fair chance that a single protocol may fail to spot all relevant structures. A systematic conformational search, which can accurately generate a set of low energy conformers, is therefore essential.³⁴⁻⁴⁰ In this study, three different protocols were followed for the conformational analysis to minimize the error in the conformational search. First, a conformational search for the low-energy structures of singly protonated LL was performed within the TINKER molecular modelling package⁴¹ using the OPLS-AA/L force field. In the second protocol, a diffusion equation evolutionary programming simulated annealing method (DEEPSAM)⁴² was used. It follows global optimization evolutionary algorithm based on hybrid PES. This locally developed algorithm was implemented in TINKER with a PYTHON wrapping and has been proven suitable for the conformational search of biomolecules.⁴² For a better precision, DEEPSAM was used with three different force fields: AmberFF99, CharmmFF27, and Oplsaa to find a pool of low energy structures. In the third protocol, the conformer library search method was based on MMFF94 force-field using Spartan14 program package. Initially, one of the lower energy structures found by the DEEPSAM search was considered. This structure was then modified by protonating its N-terminus and the conformer search of the protonated structures was performed using Spartan14. A set of lower energy structures obtained by three protocols were then optimized by B3LYP method with 6-31G(d) basis set to get a reliable set of structures. Ten lowest energy structures obtained at this level were further optimized at three different higher level of theories: B3LYP/6-31+G(d,p), B3LYP-GD2/6-31+G(d,p), and M06-2X/6-31+G(d,p).⁴³ Finally, vibrational spectra of these structures were calculated. In order to choose the best-matching structure for further VSCF calculations the scaled harmonic IR spectra of the ten lowest-energy structures were compared with experimental data. More details of conformational search are given in SI.

VSCF-PT2 approximation

The basic VSCF approximation is governed by the separable ansatz. The N -mode trial wave function is approximated as the product of single mode (i) wave function ($\psi_i^{(n)}$) as

$$\Psi(Q_1, \dots, Q_N) = \prod_{i=1}^N \psi_i^{(n)}(Q_i) \quad (1)$$

The single mode VSCF equation can, therefore, be obtained using the variational principle:

$$\left[-\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial Q_i^2} + \overline{V}_i^{(n)}(Q_i) \right] \psi_i^{(n)} = \varepsilon_i^{(n)} \psi_i^{(n)}(Q_i) \quad (2)$$

Here $\overline{V}_i^{(n)}(Q_i)$ is the effective potential for mode Q_i and can be expressed as an average-way

$$\overline{V}_i^{(n)}(Q_i) = \left\langle \prod_{j \neq i}^N \psi_j^{(n)}(Q_j) \left| V(Q_1, \dots, Q_N) \right| \prod_{j \neq i}^N \psi_j^{(n)}(Q_j) \right\rangle \quad (3)$$

Consequently, the single mode wave function and state energies can be calculated by solving eq. 2 and 3 following self-consistent method. While VSCF method is often accurate enough, it is desirable to consider the correlation effects between the vibrational modes. If the non-separability effects are small a suitable level of perturbation theory can be employed on top of the VSCF energy levels (See SI for more details) for better accuracy. Further details of the VSCF theory can be found in a recent review.⁴⁴

Pairwise coupling approximations

The numerical evaluation of the multidimensional integral in the eq. 3 is the most computationally demanding task. In the framework of independent particle model, difficulty of the integral evaluation depends on the form of the potential function. The VSCF potential, as a good approximation, can be expressed as sum of single-mode (diagonal approximation) and pair-wise coupling terms. Therefore, the equation can be written in normal coordinate (Q) as,

$$V(Q_1, \dots, Q_N) = \sum_{i=1}^N V_i^{diag}(Q_i) + \sum_j \sum_{i>j} V_{ij}^{2coup}(Q_i, Q_j) \quad (4)$$

Here, V_i^{diag} and V_{ij}^{2coup} are the 1D and 2D potentials, respectively. This functional form requires multi-dimensional grid point calculations to construct the anharmonic potential. Previous studies showed that, depending on the type of modes (rigid/semi-rigid/soft), 8 to 16 grid points per normal modes are satisfactory.^{14, 15, 26} One should be careful about the total number of grid points for a large system because it depends on the number of vibrational modes. If NG is the number of grid points for a given normal mode and NV is the total number of vibrational modes, the number of total grid points (NP) is given by

$$NP = [NV \times NG] + \frac{[NV(NV - 1) \times NG^2]}{2} \quad (5)$$

Clearly, the total number of required grid points increase sharply with the increase of NV and NG . Considering the size of the LL with

237 vibrational degrees of freedom, 8 grid points per normal modes are used to carry out the calculation in a reasonable time scale.

Choice of potential

Once the equation for the potential function and grid points (Eq. 6 and 7) is set, the choice of potential is then crucial, especially for a large systems where the balance between accuracy and computational time is subtle. It is desirable to choose first-principles based quantum mechanical methods for good accuracy. It was found that both the post-HF (such as MP2) and DFT based methods are suitable in terms of accuracy for the VSCF calculations. The former provides better accuracy than the latter, yet at the higher computational cost. However, from the perspective of vibrational structure calculation, both these methods are computationally expensive to compute the full pair-wise coupling terms for ALE. Hence, further suitable approximations are required.

The harmonic part of the potential requires the maximum accuracy as its contribution to each frequency is much larger than the anharmonic part. Consequently, the magnitude of the differences for harmonic part calculated at two different levels of theory is more significant than that of the anharmonic one. Following this fact, a hybrid potential scheme is employed by "upgrading" the PESs of a lower level calculation to more accurate anharmonic frequencies (see SI for more details).²⁵ This protocol was applied successfully for small to medium sized systems. In this study the hybrid potentials are constructed using computationally fast HF method while the harmonic potential at this level is upgraded by a more accurate MP2 method with 6-31G(d,p) basis set in both cases. Additionally, a pure pair-wise coupling potential is also considered in the DFT framework using dispersion-corrected B3LYP-D2 method with 6-31+G(d,p) basis set.

Computation of the VSCF potential of ALE including the full pair-wise coupling terms is a nearly impossible task for any level of quantum chemical theory using present state-of-the-art computers. It requires as large as 1791720 numbers of single point energy computations considering 8 grid points per normal mode. Consequently, a further approximation is required to avoid such redundant situation. It is apparent that if two modes are spatially separated, which is common for large systems, the coupling between the modes must be small and can be ignored. Following this fact, the number of full pair-wise potential terms can be truncated to a tractable size. In earlier studies this type of truncated pair-wise potentials were successfully implemented for a decapeptide gramicidin S. In this study this protocol is implemented and the computational time is thus reduced to a reasonable time scale without losing noticeable accuracy. All the VSCF calculations are performed using locally modified GAMESS program.⁴⁵

Experimental method

Our experimental approach has been described previously.⁴⁶⁻⁴⁸ Briefly, protonated, gas-phase ALE ions ($m=570.3$ Da) are produced from solution (80/20 water/methanol solution conditioned by acetic acid to pH~3) using a nano-electrospray ion source with orthogonal injection into an ion funnel guide. The ions are pre-

collected and thermalized for ~50 ms in a hexapole ion trap, mass-selected by a quadrupole mass filter, and guided into a cold octupole ion trap, maintained at $T=6$ K, where the ions are trapped and cooled by collisions with He buffer gas, pulsed into the trap shortly before the arrival of the ions. Once cooled, the ions are interrogated by UV laser and IR optical parametric oscillator (OPO) pulses of 5-6 ns duration, separated by 100 ns. The released ions are then analyzed with a quadrupole mass spectrometer, detected by a channeltron, and, finally, counted by a photon counter. The cold trap is filled in and the UV laser fires at 20 Hz repetition rate, while the IR OPO fires at 10 Hz.

An IR gain spectrum is measured by fixing UV laser wavenumber slightly to the red from the electronic band origin of an ion, where UV photofragmentation is negligible. IR pre-excitation causes a broadening and a redshift of UV absorption bands, which results in a drastic increase of UV photofragmentation yield. Measuring this yield as a function of IR OPO wavenumber generates a vibrational gain spectrum of all abundant conformers of the ions.

A conformer-selective IR-UV hole-burning spectroscopy is measured as follows. IR OPO wavenumber is sequentially fixed at the vibrationally resolved, conformer-specific vibrational transitions. Such IR pre-excitations affects UV spectrum of only the conformer that is excited by IR OPO. This technique allows for the

conformational assignment of the UV transitions and, hence, allows to determine the number of abundant conformers, present under experimental conditions.

[Ala², Leu⁵]-leucine enkephalin of >95% purity was purchased from Bachem and used without any further purification.

Fig. 2 Optimized structures of the global and first few local minima computed at B3LYP-D/6-31+G(d,p) level of theory.

Results and discussion

Table 1 lists some structural properties and zero-point corrected relative energies of ten lowest energy conformers found by using three different conformational search protocols described above and subsequently optimized by different high level DFT calculations. The seven lowest energy optimized structures of ALE are given in Figure 2.

Figure 3a shows the measured IR gain spectrum of ALE cooled to $T_{\text{vib}} \sim 10$ K. The number of peaks in the spectrum suggests the presence of only one highly abundant conformer of ALE and one minor conformer of the ion (see, for instance, the peak at 3570.4 cm^{-1}). This assignment has been verified by IR-UV hole burning spectroscopy of the peptide (See Supporting information for details). Regarding the intensities of the IR transitions, the relative population of the minor conformer has been estimated to be less than 10%.

Table 1 Conformational analysis of LL (relative energies are in kcal/mol)

Conformer	Distance between two Phe rings (Å)	H-bonding in C-terminus OH	H-bonding in all NH	Relative energy ¹	Relative energy ²
LL_0	~10-12	Yes	Yes	0.00	0.00
LL_1	~9-11	Yes	Yes	2.88	2.57
LL_2	~10-12	Yes	Yes	2.99	2.12
LL_3	~4-5	No	No	4.05	2.91
LL_4	~9-11	Yes	Yes	4.25	2.45
LL_5	~4-5	No	No	5.36	4.41
LL_6	~4-5	No	No	5.53	4.39
LL_7	~8-10	No	No	7.94	5.49
LL_8	~6-8	No	No	8.17	8.17
LL_9	~8-10	No	No	10.54	10.57
LL_10	~8-10	No	No	11.60	10.46

¹B3LYP-D/6-31+G(d,p), ²M06-2X/6-31+G(d,p)

The structure LL_0 in Table 1 corresponds to the global energy minimum at both the B3LYP-D and M06-2X levels of theory. We, therefore, calculated the IR spectrum for this structure in HO approximation at MP2/6-31G(d,p) and B3LYP/6-31G+(d,p) levels of theory. Figures 3b and 3c show the calculated scaled stick spectra. The achieved match of the calculated spectra to the experimentally measured one is quite good, particularly at the B3LYP/6-31+G(d,p) level of theory.

Fig.3 Comparison of (a) the experimental IR gain spectrum with (b-f) the scaled harmonic stick spectra of four abundant conformers of ALE. The UV laser wavenumber was fixed at 35684.53 cm^{-1} . The two peaks, labelled by asterisks, are used for IR-UV hole-burning spectroscopy (see SI for details). The traces (b) and (c) correspond to the spectra of the lowest energy structure (LL_0) computed at MP2/6-31G(d,p) and B3LYP/6-31+G(d,p) levels of theory, respectively. The traces (d)-(f) are for LL_7, LL_8 and LL_3 conformers, respectively (see table 1). The harmonic frequency values were scaled by a factor of 0.9424 and 0.9554 for (b) and (c)-(f), respectively.

We, therefore, use this level of theory to compute IR spectra for other conformers, listed in Table 1. Some of these spectra, which show the closest match to the experiment, are shown for a comparison in Figures 3d-3f. It is evident from the comparison of the calculated spectra that the computed lowest energy structure LL_0 is, presumably, the one observed in the experiment. This structure, in

Fig.4 Comparison of the experimental IR spectrum (black trace) with computed spectra of the lowest energy conformer using hybrid HF/MP2 (green trace), B3LYP-D (blue trace) and average potentials (red).

general, resembles the structure of the protonated Leu-enkephaline (YGGFL)⁵ and has a large spacing between aromatic rings of Tyr and Phe residues, as it was earlier predicted from the resonance energy transfer (FRET) measurements.⁴

Scaling of a harmonic spectrum is, however, ambiguous and, occasionally, may lead to conformational misassignments. First-principles based calculations are, therefore, essential for final structural validation. We carried out VSCF-PT2 calculations for the lowest-energy structure LL_0 using B3LYP and hybrid HF/MP2 potentials to validate the result obtained by scaled harmonic approximation. B3LYP potential with dispersion correction (at GD2 level) was used with 6-31+G(d,p) basis set for the calculation of VSCF-PT2 spectra using 13 selected vibrational modes for the pairwise coupling potential functions. For the hybrid HF/MP2 potential 6-31G(d,p) basis set was used considering 80 vibrational modes.

Table 2 provides a comparison of experimental spectra in the region of H-stretching vibrations with those computed at the anharmonic level using two different potentials. As can be seen, the overall agreement between experimental and computed transitions is good. For the first six transitions, B3LYP potential systematically underestimates the experiment, while HF/MP2 hybrid potential overestimates it by $\sim 20\text{-}50\text{ cm}^{-1}$. In both cases the VSCF-PT2 and the scaled harmonic values are quite similar, which further supports the assumption that the global minima LL_0 is the observed structure. In mixed modes, NH_3^+ combined with C-terminal OH results in a broad band around $2950\text{-}3050\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and here, again, HF/MP2 potential is shifted to the blue, while B3LYP is shifted to the red with respect to the experimental value. For the three mixed modes, large deviations are observed for two transitions at the B3LYP level. It is due to the resonance effect, inherently present in the VSCF-PT2 algorithm, which occurs occasionally and depends on the type of potential used. This can be confirmed by comparing values of VSCF-PT2 with basic VSCF, which is free from resonance effect. The VSCF values of these two transitions are closer to experiment (3002 cm^{-1} against 2755 cm^{-1} and 2848 cm^{-1} against 2740 cm^{-1}). Any perturbative method suffers from such resonance problem and for VSCF-PT2, in particular, when the harmonic values are close to each other, it can occur occasionally due to numerical instabilities. It should be mentioned that VSCF can compute transitions and intensities but not the linewidths of transitions, though the experimental peaks always have finite linewidths. Hence, VSCF transitions require to treat spectral width and line broadening which yield spectral line shapes. The Lorentzian broadening function with HWHM of 5 cm^{-1} is used to simulate the spectral line shapes in this study. Figure 4 compares the experimental data, the anharmonic transitions computed by two different protocols and the transitions, calculated as the average of these two sets of computed transitions. The average transitions exhibit the best match to the experiment for peak positions in the NH and OH stretch spectral range. This result demonstrates a complementary nature of the two types of anharmonic calculations, when certain drawbacks of one method are compensated by performance of the other. It is found that in the high-frequency range the harmonic potential calculated by B3LYP is softer than HF and MP2. The HF is most stiff, followed by MP2. Hence, both these potentials bind stronger than B3LYP potential. It is also noted that both the B3LYP and the hybrid HF/MP2 methods offer nearly similar anharmonic corrections ($\nu_{\text{harm}} - \nu_{\text{anharm}}$), which shows that both methods are

close in estimating the anharmonicity. Consequently, the overall accuracy of the final computed transitions depends on the accuracy of the harmonic part, and the magnitude of the anharmonic corrections may converge theory toward the experimental values. When the harmonic potential is soft, the anharmonic correction may shift the transition to the red from the experiment, which is the case for B3LYP potential. On the other hand, HF/MP2 potential, being stiffer, resides to the blue from the experiment. The pattern of such red-blue shifts of these two potentials indicates that their average may provide better accuracy compared to the individual values. Table 2 and Figure 4 show the results of such spectral averaging. For H-stretches of Tyr, Phe, Gly, Ala, and Leu the deviations governed by B3LYP and HF/MP2 potentials (typically, a few tens of wavenumbers) are cancelled out in the averaged spectrum, resulting in discrepancies with the experiment of a few

wavenumber (typically below 10 cm^{-1}) which is a significant step forward as far as accuracy between experiment and computation transitions is concerned. A more detailed study in this direction is required. Finally, the overall agreement of the first-principles based calculations of electronic and vibrational spectra with experiment firmly validates the intrinsic structure of the lowest energy structure of ALE. This study shows the predictive power of the state-of-the-art theory for solving the conformational specific structures of large biomolecules.

Table 2. Comparison of experiment with calculated harmonic, scaled harmonic and anharmonic fundamental transitions of the global minima of LL-enkephaline. Scale factor is 0.95. Intensities are given in the parenthesis. VSCF values are given in italics with square brackets

Stretching modes	Exp	HF	MP2		HF/MP2	B3LYP-D			Avg. ¹
		HO	HO	scaled-HO	VSCF-PT2	HO	scaled-HO	VSCF-PT2	
OH (Tyr)	3648	4041	3871	3677	3684 (106)	3816	3625	3595 (97)	3639.5
NH (Phe)	3406	3859	3642	3456	3466 (106)	3565	3387	3363 (166)	3414.5
NH (Gly)	3384	3852	3634	3452	3458 (121)	3540	3363	3342 (192)	3400.0
NH (Ala)	3377	3814	3614	3433	3435 (187)	3529	3353	3332 (150)	3383.5
NH (Leu)	3321	3806	3566	3388	3389 (116)	3486	3312	3269 (233)	3329.0
NH ₃ ⁺	3289	3714	3544	3367	3353 (182)	3461	3288	3273 (180)	3313.0
NH ₃ ⁺ (major) + C-terminus OH (minor) (Mixed Modes)	2977	3570	3270	3107	3064 (241)	3189	3030	2755 [3002] (392)	3033.0
	2948	3419	3324	3158	3062 (812)	3150	2993	2956 (1403)	3009.0
C-terminus OH (major) + NH ₃ ⁺ (minor) (Mixed Modes)	3036	3725	3240	3078	3065 (259)	3144	2987	2740 [2848] (170)	2902.5

¹average VSCF-PT2 values calculated at HF/MP2 and B3LYP-D methods

Conclusions

This work demonstrates that the systematic conformational analysis, first-principles based quantum mechanical calculations for electronic structure, and suitable anharmonic molecular vibrational approach using *ab initio* PESs provide unbiased structural determination for a system as large as a pentapeptide. The most stable structure of [Ala², Leu⁵]-leucine enkephalin has been unambiguously solved herein from the first-principles. It exhibits the distance between the aromatic rings of Phe and Tyr residues as large as 11.2 Å, which was previously predicted from FRET measurements⁴ performed by 2D UV-MS fingerprinting.^{2, 49} The computed lowest-energy structure has been validated through a comparison of the measurements with the vibrational spectrum calculated at the anharmonic level of theory without a use of any

adjustable parameters. Although none of the two anharmonic methods employed here alone does not provide a sufficient accuracy in reproducing the experimental IR spectrum, the average of the two calculated spectra exhibits a level of match that is comparable to the scaled-HO approximation. The averaging mutually compensates the known tendency of the B3LYP and HF/MP2 potentials to under/over-calculate anharmonic vibrational frequencies. The demonstrated here technique of averaging can be explored for different large molecular systems. The anharmonic part of the calculated PES can be further used for computing additional molecular properties, for instance, the intramolecular vibrational dynamics.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank Leah Reiss for participating in some calculations. TKR thanks DST-SERB-EMR (grant no. EMR/2017/000512) for financial support and Central University of Jammu for infrastructural facility. OVB thanks Swiss National Science Foundation for supporting this work through the grants200020_159918 and 200020_172522 / 1.

References

- S. R. Mercier, O. V. Boyarkin, A. Kamariotis, M. Guglielmi, I. Tavernelli, M. Cascella, U. Rothlisberger and R. T. R., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **128**, 16938-16943.
- V. Kopysov, A. Makarov and O. V. Boyarkin, *Anal. Chem.*, 2015, **87**, 4607-4611.
- T. Rizzo and O. V. Boyarkin, *Top. Curr. Chem.*, 2014, **364**, 43-97.
- V. Kopysov and O. V. Boyarkin, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed*, 2016, **55**, 689-692.
- N. L. Burke, J. G. Redwine, J. C. Dean, S. A. McLuckey and T. S. Zwier, *Int. J. Mass. Spec.*, 2015, **378**, 196-205.
- G. Féraud, C. Dedonder, C. Jouvét, Y. Inokuchi, T. Haino, R. Sekiya and T. Ebata, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.*, 2014, **5**, 1236-1240.
- E. Garand, M. Z. Kamrath, P. A. Jordan, A. B. Wolk, C. M. Leavitt, A. B. McCoy, S. J. Miller and M. A. Johnson, *Science*, 2012, **333**, 694-698.
- M. S. de Vries and P. Hobza, *Ann. Rev. Phys. Chem.*, 2007, **58**, 585-612.
- A. F. DeBlase, C. P. Harrilal, J. T. Lawler, N. L. Burke, S. A. McLuckey and T. S. Zwier, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2017, **139**, 5481-5493.
- J. M. Bowman, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1978, **68**, 608-610.
- R. B. Gerber and M. A. Ratner, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1979, **68**, 195-198.
- J. M. Bowman, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1986, **19**, 202-208.
- J. M. Bowman, S. Carter and X. C. Huang, *Int. Rev. Phys. Chem*, 2003, **22**, 533-549.
- T. K. Roy, T. Carrington Jr. and R. B. Gerber, *J. Phys. Chem. A*, 2014, **118**, 6730-6739.
- T. K. Roy, R. Sharma and R. B. Gerber, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2016, **16**.
- L. Pele, J. Sebek, E. O. Potma and R. B. Gerber, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2011, **515**, 7-12.
- K. Meng and J. Wang, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2011, **13**, 2001-2013.
- O. Christiansen, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2007, **9**, 2942-2953.
- T. K. Roy and M. D. Prasad, *J. Chem. Sci.*, 2009, **121**, 805-810.
- G. Rauhut, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2004, **121**, 9313-9322.
- Y. Scribano and D. M. Benoit, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2007, **127**, 164118-164118.
- R. B. Gerber, B. Brauer, S. K. Gregurick and G. M. Chaban, *PhysChemComm*, 2002, **5**, 142-150.
- B. Brauer, M. Pincu, V. Buch, I. Bar, J. P. Simons and R. B. Gerber, *J. Phys. Chem. A*, 2011, **115**, 5859-5872.
- B. Brauer, R. B. Gerber, M. Kabeláč, P. Hobza, J. M. Bakker, A. G. A. Riziq and M. S. de Vries, *J. Phys. Chem. A*, 2005, **109**, 6974-6984.
- B. Brauer, G. M. Chaban and R. B. Gerber, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2004, **6**, 2543-2556.
- T. K. Roy, V. Kopysov, N. S. Nagornova, T. R. Rizzo, O. V. Boyarkin and R. B. Gerber, *ChemPhysChem*, 2015, DOI: **10.1002/cphc.201500085**.
- T. K. Roy, N. S. Nagornova, O. V. Boyarkin and R. B. Gerber, *J. Phys. Chem. A*, 2017, **121**, 9401-9408.
- M. P. Gaijeot, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2010, **12**, 3336-3359.
- A. Cimas, T. D. Vaden, T. S. J. A. de Boer, L. C. Snoek and M. P. Gaijeot, *J. Chem. Theor. Comp.*, 2009, **5**, 1068-1078.
- V. Barone, *J. Phys. Chem. A*, 2004, **108**, 4146-4150.
- J. Bloino, M. Biczysko and V. Barone, *J. Chem. Theor. Comp.*, 2012, **8**, 1015-1036.
- G. Avila and T. Carrington Jr., *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2012, **137**, 174108-174113.
- L. S. Norris, M. A. Ratner, A. E. Roitberg and R. B. Gerber, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1996, **105**, 11261-11267.
- C. Baldauf, K. Pagel, S. Warnke, G. von Helden, B. Koksich, V. Blum and M. Scheffler, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2013, **19**, 11224-11234.
- S. Chutia, M. Rossi and V. Blum, *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 2012, **116**, 14788-14804.
- L. Voronina, A. Masson, M. Kamrath, F. Schubert, D. Clemmer, C. Baldauf and T. Rizzo, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2016, **138**, 9224-9233.
- C. Puzzarini and V. Barone, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2018, **51**, 548-556.

38. C. P. Harrilal, A. DeBlase, F., J. L. Fischer, J. T. Lawler, S. A. McLuckey and T. S. McLuckey, *J. Am. Chem. A*, **122**, 2096-2107.
39. H. Otaki, Y. K., S. Ishiuchi, M. Fujii and Y. Sugita, *J. Am. Chem. B*, 2016, **120**, 10199-10213.
40. P. T. Panek and C. R. Jacob, *J. Am. Chem. Lett.*, 2016, **7**, 3084-3090.
41. J. A. Rackers, M. L. Laury, C. Lu, Z. Wang, L. Lagardère, J.-P. Piquemal, P. Ren and J. W. Ponder, *TINKER 8: A Modular Software Package for Molecular Design and Simulation*, 2017.
42. M. Goldstein, E. Fredj and R. B. Gerber, *J. Comp. Chem.*, 2010, **32**, 1785-1800.
43. Y. Zhao and D. G. Truhlar, *Theor. Chem. Acc.*, 2006, **120**, 215-241.
44. T. K. Roy and R. B. Gerber, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2013, **15**, 9468-9492.
45. M. W. Schmidt, K. K. Baldridge, J. A. Boatz, S. T. Elbert, M. S. Gordon, J. H. Jensen, S. Koseki, N. Matsunaga, K. A. Nguyen, S. J. Su, T. L. Windus, M. Dupuis and J. A. Montgomery, *J. Comput. Chem.*, 1993, **14**, 1347-1363.
46. V. Kopysov, N. S. Nagomova and O. V. Boyarkin, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2014, **136**, 9288-9291.
47. A. Y. Pereverzev, N. S. Nagomova and O. V. Boyarkin, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2017, **19**, 3468-3472.
48. A. Y. Pereverzev, V. Kopysov and O. V. Boyarkin, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2017, DOI: **10.1002/anie.201709437**.
49. V. Kopysov, M. V. Gorshkov and O. V. Boyarkin, *Analyst*, 2018, **143**, 833-836.